

BIO4 PRODUCTS

Creating sustainable resources for process industry

Where in Europe could we imagine a fast pyrolysis based biorefinery?

Our new report has identified four potential locations for lignocellulosic biorefineries based on the availability and quality of biomass in Europe

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NEW PUBLICATION

Virtual pyrolysis plant locations in Europe

Availability and quality of biomass resources at four potential sites

BIO4PRODUCTS REPORT ON VIRTUAL PYROLYSIS PLANTS PUBLISHED

Capax Biobased Development has identified four 'Virtual Pyrolysis Plant' locations where biorefineries could be established.

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MEET THE TEAM #2

CAPAX BIOBASED DEVELOPMENT

Capax Biobased Development (also known as Capax Environmental services) is a Belgian SME that specialises in turning biobased projects into success.

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SEE YOU THERE?

BIO4PRODUCTS WILL BE AT NWBC IN HELSINKI NEXT WEEK

BTG wil present at the Nordic Wood Biorefinery Conference in Helsinki, Finland on 23-25 October 2018

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BIOECONOMY NEWS

EU PUBLISHES UPDATED BIOECONOMY STRATEGY

The European Commission has announced a set of 14 concrete actions to be launched by 2019.

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BIO-BASED PRODUCTS GET BOOST IN UNITED STATES

12 new product categories have been added to the USDA BioPreferred programme for public procurement

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 723070.

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